

*ANALYSIS OF THE TERMS "PUL", "ДЕНЬГИ", AND "MONEY" IN COGNITIVE
LINGUISTICS*

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Annotation: Since all of these stable units conceptualize ideas that are important to people—especially the concept of "money" that interests us, the paper deals with phraseological units, the proverbial fund, and aphoristic language. The content utilized in the project allowed for the viewing of examples of how the concept of moral and spiritual relationships was represented in the Uzbek, English, and Russian funds of stable units and how the language used to convey these concepts was applied in the conventional structures of stable national units.

Annotatsiya: Maqolada frazeologik birliklar va maqollar fondi, shuningdek, aforistik masalalar ko'rib chiqiladi, chunki bu barqaror birliklarning barchasi xalqlar uchun ahamiyatli bo'lgan tushunchalarni, xususan, bizni qiziqtiradigan "pul" tushunchalarini ifodalaydi. Ishda foydalanilgan material rus, ingliz va o'zbek turg'un birliklar fondida ma'naviy, axloqiy munosabatlar g'oyasi qanday aks etganligi va bu kategoriyalarni ifodalashning til vositalarining tipik konstruksiyalarida qanday amalga oshirilganligi misollarini ko'rish imkonini berdi.

Аннотация: В статье рассматриваются фразеологизмы и пословичный фонд, а также афористические, поскольку все эти устойчивые единицы концептуализируют значимые для народов понятия, в частности, интересующие нас «деньги». Использованный в работе материал позволил увидеть примеры того, как идея духовно-этических отношений отразилась в русском, английском и узбекском фонде устойчивых единиц и как языковые средства выражения этих категорий реализовались в типичных конструкциях национальные конюшни.

Keywords: national and cultural coloring, concept money, phraseological units, stable units, and people's mentalities.

Kalit so'zlar: milliy-madaniy kolorit, pul tushunchasi, frazeologik birliklar, turg'un birliklar, xalq mentaliteti.

Ключевые слова: национально-культурная окраска, концепт-деньги, фразеологизмы, устойчивые единицы, менталитет народа.

The material under study demonstrated that the phraseological field of the notion "money" possesses a cultural and national flavor. There is a core, a nearby peripheral, and a distant periphery to the phraseological field of the idea of "money" in the languages of Uzbekistan, English, and Russia. The central idea of the phraseological field containing the word "money" comprises 250 phraseological units in Russian, 270 phraseological units in English, and 267 phraseological units in Uzbek. This suggests that these English language units have more functional activity, which seems to reflect the unique mentalities of this individuals.

Within the lexico-semantic gather of the close fringe within the circle of phraseological units having a common meaning, counting the seme "cash", 60 units were recognized in Russian, 90 units in English; in Uzbek 75 units. Clearly, the tall predominance of the names "cash" (particularly slang ones) within the diction of the English dialect indicates a extraordinary consideration to this marvel appeared by this country. The foremost branched in all three dialects is the distant fringe.

Within the whole cluster of phraseological units with the meaning a "money", from the point of view of phonetic implications in all three dialects, units of a procedural sort (around 45%), demonstrative nature (approximately 30%), phraseological units with a subjective meaning are few (around 15%). In English figures of speech, the procedural phonetic meaning is more significant than in Russian and Uzbek, particularly within the commerce circle, and the subject linguistic meaning is more point by point (around 25%). Clearly, this can be a reflection of a more down to business approach to cash and riches within the Anglo-Saxon world, so the manner of the English dialect is more judicious compared to Russian and Uzbek.

Comparison of the conceptualization of "cash" in Russian, English and Uzbek idiomatic highlights the critical focuses of the phraseologization of the concept: the common thing is that the concept beneath think about in idiomatic is totally human-centric, in differentiate to the lexicalized one; in all three dialects, a generally little set of genuine implications is compensated by the wealthy symbolism of the inside frame of figures of speech; the concept of "cash" within the three societies gets an increase of riches, gold and other fabric values, which are showed in huge amounts, and life in this state is simple, wonderful and carefree. The differences are watched within the truth that, for example, for the Russian awareness, cash isn't the premise for the metaphorization of human qualities, within the English dialect there are only confined cases of metaphorization of human qualities through the concept of "cash", whereas within the Uzbek dialect such representations are visit.

Hence, the phraseological (informal) foundation, in differentiate to the lexical one, passes on nonconceptual semantic offers in a complex way, more often than not with all its components in their resoluteness, reacting to the most nature of manner - idiomaticity.

The paremiological representation of the concept "cash" constitutes a transitional zone from the phonetic to the literary (interpretative) layer of their presence. As a result of the examination of 300 Russian, 320 English and 305 Uzbek maxims, we note that paremiological conceptualizations in Russian, English and Uzbek make up a complex arrange of resistances and commonly elite articulations. Widespread values (what cash cannot purchase) incorporate wellbeing, insights, activity, cherish, influence, bliss, great title, time, honor, companions, and satisfaction. To particular ones in Russian -father and mother, soul, truth, goodness, God, cheerful mien; in English - luckiness, guarantee, the word of a man; in Uzbek - great times, honor.

Comparative investigation of English, Russian and Uzbek paremias of the field "Cash / Cash / Argent" permits us to draw the taking after conclusions: the most differences are famous within the arrangement of the field; the Russian world renowned field is more characteristic of semantic opposition than the English and Uzbek ones; within the Russian certifiable field, the national-cultural component is more articulated due to the more noteworthy number of names of national banknotes, names of national realities appropriate names. Within the English and Uzbek dialects, thenational-cultural component is basically communicated as it were by the setup of the field of adages.

Aphoristics as a scholarly sort is inalienable in tall culture. Concurring to the guideline of substance, deontic and alethic all inclusive articulations are recognized. The winning number of alethic widespread articulations was famous (80% in Russian, 75% in English, 70% in Uzbek). In some cases these articulations are given a ethical / positive or miliorative / deprecatory appraisal. Regularly the articulations of the creators of axioms are communicated incomprehensibly, and in the event that a adage sets a certain generalization, at that point the truism devastates it,

communicating a to be perfectly honest amusing meaning. Axioms reflect social universals, sayings are more frequently carriers of particular national characteristics. When considering the substance of the semantic structure of the aphoristic field "cash", "cash", "argent", we found the coincidence of the substance least of the concept "cash" - a positive demeanor towards cash is showed in all three societies. The recognized conceptual bunches of axioms incorporate both synonymous and antonymous axioms, which affirms the truth that the concept of "cash" alludes to the foremost critical social universals. Due to the all inclusiveness of the concept of "money" beneath think about, in three dialects, in common, the same extralinguistic variables of states of mind towards cash in different circles of their presence, consistent laws of mental handling of data approximately the world through the concept of "money" are common to all individuals. Cash could be a implies of survival, cash is an necessarily portion of life, cash brings joy, adore and money are interconnected, cash is quality, cash may be a living being. The semantic space of the Russian, English and Uzbek dialects is based on all inclusive thoughts around cash and state of mind to them, which is affirmed by the distinguishing proof of universal concepts as the consistent premise of the picture of the world within the Russian, English and Uzbek dialects. All dialectsexpress the thought that cash alone cannot bring internal peace, joy and fulfillment. In any case, indeed in destitution a individual cannot discover satisfaction, bliss and meaning in life.

Intelligence proposes that the arrangement to this situation that a individual so frequently faces is to endeavor to ended up such a individual who is regarded in himself and at the same time pulls in cash, since genuine riches comprises within the nearness of a entirety complex of conditions, counting and wellbeing, and budgetary prosperity, and assurance, and tirelessness, and perseverance, and information, and ethical quality, and benevolence, and confidence, and adore, and internal peace, and otherworldly existence. Be that as it may, within the attitude of each country, a distinctive substance of the same concept of "money" is decided, due to which the picture of the world obtains a national-specific coloring, both in terms of expression and in terms of substance. We accept that the broadly particular substance of the concept of "cash" is due to the distinctive encounter of cognition of reality and the idiosyncrasies of the evaluative movement of a specific individuals.

The conceptualization of the concept of "cash" finds different expressions within the dialect through lexical and phraseological units within the frame of signs of attitude towards money displayed in them. The concept could be a multidimensional arrangement, counting metaphorical, conceptual-definitional and normative evaluative characteristics.

Conceptualization: 1) The method of the rise of semantic increases in units of diverse levels from a word to a content - objective, creating the implications of the word displayed within the word reference, and subjective, affiliated with objective increases in smaller scale- and large scale writings;

1) The incremental values themselves coming about from the activity of this prepare.

Within the presence of the concept of "cash" in Russian, English and Uzbek dialects, widespread and broadly particular highlights are reflected. All inclusive signs make up the center layer of the concept "cash" and are transcendently cognitive in nature, whereas particular signs are basically fringe layers of the concept and are related with both social and phonetic highlights.

The lexical representation of the concept of "cash" uncovers its conceptual appearance, covers the center layer and has both human-centric and non-anthropocentric characteristics.

Contrasts within the lexical implies of objectifying the conceptual space of cash are the result of the appearance of the person highlights of the national dialect.

The informal representation of the concept "cash" illustrates beside the conceptual, metaphorical, allegorical and typical signs and is an human-centric characteristic. Figures of speech with the "money" component are characterized by expanded emotionality and figurativeness, based on a extraordinary recognition of the marvels and actualities of the encompassing reality, on their appraisal (positive or negative). There are bunches of phraseological units with common incremental implications (cash - duplicity, cash - quality, control, cash - a living being, cash - stresses, cash - labor) and bunches of phraseological units with national-specific intentions that reflect the mindset and creativity of the culture of Russian, English and Uzbek people groups: (in Russian: cash - earth, awful metal, terrible papers; in English: cash - a beneficial accomplice, compensate; in Uzbek: cash - good fortune, joy, extravagance, brilliance, splendor).

The paremiological representation of the concept of "cash" constitutes a transitional zone from phonetic to literary (person) presence. Paroemias uncover the irresolute state of mind of a local speaker of Russian, English and Uzbek to cash, the paremiological finance is characterized by commonly select conceptualizations inside the same concept.

Axioms possess an halfway position between a saying and an standard author's articulation. The social and phonetic characteristics of Russian, English and Uzbek adages and axioms affirm to a certain contrast between the compared societies in connection to conventional collective esteem implications and the vicinity of the compared societies in connection to the person esteem picture of the world reflected in axioms.

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